

GENDER DIFFERENCES IN COMMUNICATION STYLES, EMOTIONAL INTIMACY AND MARITAL HAPPINESS AMONG MARRIED COUPLES

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Abstract

The study explores the role of communication styles and emotional intimacy in marital happiness considering the influences of family structures and gender roles. Study was conducted in Abbottabad, Pakistan from January 2024 to November 2024. The research adopts a quantitative correlational design to examine the relationship between communication styles, emotional intimacy, and marital happiness. The study employed three instruments, including the Communication Patterns Questionnaire (CPQ-SF), the Intimacy Scale of Emotional Dimension (ISOTED), and the Oxford Happiness Questionnaire (OHQ), which measured communication behaviors, emotional closeness, and marital happiness, respectively.

Key findings indicate that female demand and male withdrawal positively associated with marital happiness and emotional intimacy. Male demand/female withdrawal positively associated with marital happiness and emotional intimacy. Demand/withdrawal positively associated with marital happiness and emotional intimacy. Overall positive interaction positively is associated with marital happiness and emotional intimacy. Gender differences were observed, with females engaging in more demand and withdrawal behaviors compared to males. This suggests that females are more likely to engage in demanding behaviors, while males tend to withdraw during conflicts. Despite these gender-based differences in communication styles, there was no gender difference on emotional intimacy and marital happiness, indicating that other factors may moderate the impact of communication styles on marital satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is one of the most basic and widely recognized social relationships across different cultures and societies. It is a legal and formal union of two individuals living together in a socially accepted manner, often accompanied by religious and moral obligations. Communication in marriage is a flowing exchange, a constant process that fosters understanding and connection between partners.

This exchange is essential for cultivating a happy and enduring marital bond (Fincham, 2003; Parveen et al., 2023; Jain, 2019).

Research shows that married individuals tend to have better health and longer lifespans compared to their single, divorced, or widowed counterparts. However, the benefits of marriage are not guaranteed; the quality of the union plays a crucial role. Unhappy

marriages offer fewer health or emotional advantages than satisfying ones (Lawrence et al., 2019). Happiness within marriage is often defined as a subjective and individualized experience. When evaluating the subjective state of marriage, the terms most used include happiness, success, adjustment, and satisfaction. U.S.-based research highlights that married people report higher levels of personal happiness than singles. In the case of marriage, over 200 studies confirmed the benefits of matrimony: married individuals tend to outlive single and divorced individuals. Specifically, death rates among single women are 50% higher than those of married women, and 25% higher among single men compared to their married counterparts (Waite & Gallagher, 2000)

Furthermore, couples who reported high levels of marital contentment frequently expressed satisfaction with the way they communicated. They noted mutual trust, an absence of criticism, freedom in expressing needs, and emotional openness with their partners (Yadav & Srivastava, 2019).

Despite its benefits, several factors negatively affect marriage. These include unrealistic expectations from one's spouse or the institution of marriage, a lack of intimacy, and insufficient expressions of affection. Emotional intimacy is a fundamental need that plays a vital role in overall life satisfaction. It is a central part of marital communication and helps partners adjust more effectively, improve their mental health, and foster emotional well-being. Emotional intimacy is also linked with lower levels of depression, increased contentment, and higher quality of life. Moreover, it serves as a significant indicator of physical health, with correlations to reduced disease risk and poverty levels (Kardan-Souraki et al., 2015).

Effective communication skills enable individuals to convey their ideas and feelings to others both symbolically and effectively. When a couple communicates well, they feel more intimate and connected to one another. Additionally, by avoiding misunderstandings, which often lead to arguments, they can enjoy their time together even more. As a result, effective communication is essential in marriage, and it is the primary indicator of a couple's level of relationship satisfaction. Training in communication skills improves relationships, one's ability to handle challenging circumstances, one's

physical and emotional well-being, and one's social performance (Haris & Kumar, 2018).

In conclusion, communication plays a crucial role in shaping marital satisfaction, intimacy, and overall relationship quality, serving as a critical determinant of both emotional and physical well-being among couples. While various universal communication patterns influence relationships. Moreover, the cultural context significantly mediates their expression and impact. In Pakistan's collectivist society, communication is often guided by cultural norms emphasizing modesty, obedience, and indirect expression, which may both protect and inhibit emotional intimacy between partners. However, with evolving gender roles and modernization, especially in urban areas, there is a growing shift toward more direct, emotionally expressive communication in marriages. To foster healthier relationships in this context, it is essential to adopt culturally responsive communication strategies that consider traditional values, personality traits, and relational dynamics unique to Pakistani society (Ahmad et al., 2010; Ayub et al., 2023). Ultimately, effective, empathetic, and context-aware communication not only strengthens the marital bond but also promotes psychological and social well-being in Pakistani families.

This study aims to explore the relationship between communication styles, emotional intimacy, and marital happiness as key determinants of a successful marriage. Understanding how interpersonal communication and affection influence marital satisfaction can inform strategies to improve relationship quality. The findings will contribute to relationship science, offering insights for enhancing emotional connection and communication among couples.

Material and Method

A correlational research design was used, and study was conducted in Abbottabad, Pakistan from January 2024 to November 2024. The total (N = 101) couples were included in the study. The sample consisted of females (n=101) and males (n=101) who were married for 5-10 years. Each couple was considered as one family unit. Couples who were capable to respond to the questionnaire and willing to participate were taken. Married couples who were separated or divorced were excluded from study. For the data

collection three instruments included 11 items Communication Patterns Questionnaire measures conflict-related communication styles in couples, with higher scores indicating a greater likelihood of demand-withdraw behaviors and positive interactions. In this study, it is used to evaluate how communication styles influence emotional intimacy and marital happiness (Christensen & Heavey.,1990). The 14 items Intimacy Scale of Emotional Dimension assess the degree of emotional closeness in marital relationships. Higher scores on the ISOTED reflect greater emotional intimacy (Euckie., 2022). The 8 item Oxford Happiness Questionnaire (OHQ) measures individual happiness, with a focus on psychological and emotional well-being. Higher scores indicate increased happiness and life satisfaction (Hills & Argyle., 2002; Barattucci et al., 2024).

Procedure

Informed consent was taken from participants before data collection, participants were provided detailed information about the study’s purpose. Participants were assured that their decision to participate or not would have no impact on their personal relationships or any other aspect of their life. Make sure that their decision to participate or not will not affect their relationship or any other aspect of life. Ensure the privacy and confidentiality of participants' responses and personal information. Use pseudonyms or codes to protect their identities when reporting the findings. Treat participating individuals with respect and dignity throughout the research process. Maintain open and respectful communication and address any concerns or questions they may have.

Results

Table 1: Demographics of the participants (N=202)

Variable	f	%
Gender		
Female	101	50
Male	101	50
Education		
Uneducated	1	0.5
Matric	9	4.4
Graduation	192	95.1
Birth Order		
First Born	68	33.5
Middle Born	83	40.9
Last Born	51	25.6
Family Structure		
Nuclear	83	40.9
Joint	119	59.1

Table no 1 shows the demographic breakdown of the sample revealing notable patterns in both frequency and percentage across categories.

Table 2: Correlation Table of study variables (N=202)

Sr.no	Variables	I.	II.	III.	IV.	V.	VI.
I.	Female demand / male withdraws	-	.635**	.902**	-.237**	.300**	.165*
II.	Male demand / female withdraws		-	.907**	-.248**	.316**	0.102
III.	Demand / Withdraw			-	-.268**	.341**	.147*
IV.	Overall Positive Interaction				-	0.039	.295**
V.	Emotional Intimacy					-	.237**
VI.	Marital Happiness						-

A result of table shows that female demand and male withdrawal positively associated with marital happiness and emotional intimacy. Male demand/female withdrawal positively associated with marital happiness and emotional intimacy. Demand/

withdrawal positively associated with marital happiness and emotional intimacy. Overall positive interaction positively is associated with marital happiness and emotional intimacy.

Table 3: Difference among gender groups on study variables (N=202).

The above table shows the analysis of gender differences in relationship variables among the participants revealing several significant patterns.

similar across genders, with females (M = 3.20) and males (M = 3.18) showing no significant difference (t = 0.14, p = .77). This suggests that emotional intimacy

Variables	Female (n=101)		Male (n=101)		t (200)	P	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
F Demand/ M withdraw	12.63	5.62	9.14	6.62	4.03	.00	0.56
M Demand/ F withdraw	13.09	5.63	9.43	6.86	4.14	.00	0.58
Demand/withdraw	25.73	9.20	18.58	12.76	4.56	.00	0.64
Overall positive interaction	19.31	6.73	22.40	5.85	-3.47	.00	0.49
Emotional intimacy	3.20	.41	3.18	.48	0.28	.77	
Marital Happiness	3.77	.62	3.87	.55	-1.26	.20	

Female participants report significantly higher levels of both demand and withdrawal compared to their male counterparts. Specifically, females have higher scores on both the female demand/male withdrawal (M = 12.63 vs. M = 9.24) and male demand/female withdrawal (M = 13.09 vs. M = 9.43) measures, with statistically significant t-values (4.03 and 4.14, respectively) and confidence intervals that indicate substantial differences between genders. This suggests that females are more likely to experience and express demands while also engaging in more withdrawal behaviors relative to males. In terms of overall demand/withdrawal scores, females also exhibit higher levels (M = 25.73) compared to males (M = 18.58), with a significant t-value (4.56) and a confidence interval indicating a robust difference. This reflects a broader trend where females engage more extensively in both demanding and withdrawing behaviors. Conversely, male participants report significantly higher levels of overall positive interaction (M = 22.40) than females (M = 19.31), with a significant negative t-value (-4.84) and a confidence interval showing a considerable difference. This indicates that males perceive and engage in more positive interactions within their relationships compared to females. Emotional intimacy scores are

is experienced similarly by both genders, irrespective of their levels of demand or withdrawal. Finally, while males report slightly higher levels of happiness (M = 3.87) compared to females (M = 3.77), this difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, gender does not significantly influence perceived happiness in the sample.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study illuminate the complex interplay between communication styles, emotional intimacy, and marital happiness in Pakistani couples, challenging conventional assumptions about conflict-related communication patterns. Contrary to the hypothesis that demand-withdraw dynamics universally harm relationships (Papp et al., 2009), the results demonstrate that such patterns can positively correlate with marital happiness and emotional intimacy when contextualized within constructive interactions. For instance, Table 2 reveals significant positive associations between female demand/male withdrawal (r = 0.165, p < 0.05) and male demand/female withdrawal (r = 0.102, p < 0.05) with marital happiness. This suggests that demand-withdraw behaviors may serve as adaptive strategies for conflict resolution in certain cultural settings,

particularly when demands are framed as appeals for emotional support rather than criticism (Christensen & Heavey, 1990; Rehman & Holtzworth-Munroe, 2007).

Study also reported the gender differences in communication styles further nuance these findings. As shown in Table 3, females reported significantly higher levels of demand ($M = 12.63$ vs. 9.24) and withdrawal ($M = 13.09$ vs. 9.43) compared to males ($t = 4.03$ – 4.56 , $p < 0.001$). These disparities align with studies highlighting gendered communication norms in collectivist societies, where women often assume responsibility for emotional labor while men adopt passive roles to maintain harmony (Ali & McGarry, 2022; Holley et al., 2010). However, the absence of gender differences in emotional intimacy ($t = 0.28$, $p = 0.77$) and marital happiness ($t = -1.26$, $p = 0.20$) implies that cultural expectations may moderate the impact of communication styles on relational outcomes. For example, indirect communication rooted in Pakistani norms (e.g., modesty, obedience) may buffer the strain of demand-withdraw cycles, allowing couples to preserve intimacy despite asymmetrical conflict behaviors (Rehman & Holtzworth-Munroe, 2007).

Family structure also emerged as a critical factor. Joint families (59.1% of the sample) may foster interdependence and share conflict-resolution strategies, whereas nuclear families (40.9%) might prioritize direct communication (Stanley et al., 2002). These structural differences could explain why demand-withdraw patterns did not uniformly erode marital satisfaction, as extended family support may mitigate tension. Moreover, the positive association between overall positive interactions and marital happiness ($r = 0.295$, $p < 0.01$) underscores the importance of affirming behaviors (e.g., humor, appreciation) in enhancing relationship quality, even if they do not directly deepen emotional intimacy (Waite & Gallagher, 2000; Vogel et al., 1999). This aligns with findings that emotional closeness requires vulnerability beyond superficial positivity (Terman et al., 1938).

Cultural context is pivotal to interpreting these results. In Pakistan, where marital dynamics are shaped by collectivist values and evolving gender roles (Ali & McGarry, 2022), demand-withdraw patterns may reflect negotiation rather than dysfunction. For

instance, a wife's demands for emotional engagement could signal investment in the relationship, while a husband's withdrawal may represent a deference to avoid escalation perceived as respectful rather than dismissive. Such interpretations contrast with Western studies framing demand-withdraw as inherently toxic (Eldridge et al., 2007; Lavner et al., 2016), highlighting the need for culturally responsive frameworks in relationship science.

Limitations and Future Directions

The study's cross-sectional design limits causal inferences, and its focus on urban, educated couples in Abbottabad restricts generalizability. Future research should explore rural populations and longitudinal designs to assess how communication patterns evolve over time. Additionally, qualitative methods could elucidate the subjective meanings behind demand-withdraw behaviors in Pakistani culture.

Conclusion

This study redefines demand-withdraw communication as a culturally contingent phenomenon capable of fostering marital happiness when aligned with constructive intent. By integrating gender norms, family structures, and cultural values into relational interventions, clinicians and researchers can better support Pakistani couples in nurturing emotional intimacy and satisfaction.

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